

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

BALANCE OF ELECTRICAL ENERGY IN ELECTRICAL NETWORKS AND COMMERCIAL LOSS ANALYSIS

Ibadov Chingiz Shafi

PhD in economics,

"Azerishiq" Open Joint Stock Company

Abstract

Electricity is an indispensable element of our daily life. When electricity is used inefficiently, technical and non-technical losses occur at the stages from power plants where energy is produced to the point of consumption. Reduction of these losses is defined as the main goal for more efficient use of existing energy systems. Since the increase in electricity tariffs due to inflation is happening all over the world, it creates conditions for the illegal consumption (theft) of electricity without accounting. For this reason, reducing the illegal consumption of electricity and compensating the financial losses of the distribution companies remains the main problem. [1] According to research, the countries of the world lose 89.3 billion annually from the theft of electricity. The US dollar is losing. The largest losses were in India (16.2 billion US dollars), followed by Brazil (10.5 billion US dollars), Russia (5.1 billion US dollars) [2]. About 50% of the total cost of non-technical (commercial) losses of electricity in the Russian Federation (according to preliminary estimates, 30 billion kWh) is accounted for by unaccounted (unmetered, non-contractual, etc.) consumption of electricity. [2]

The rate of loss and theft in the Republic of Turkey is still higher than the rate of loss and theft in developed countries. For instance, according to the reports of Vangölü Elektrik Dağıtım A.Ş. (VEDAS), connected to the Van, Bitlis and Hakkari provinces, as of the end of 2017, the loss and theft rates were 72% in Hakkari, 53% in Van, 48.5% in Mus and Bitlis. It is shown to be 35%. [7]

These issues still remain a problem in our republic. So, despite the serious struggle against the illegal use of electricity in "Bakielektrikshebeke" OJSC, and later in "Azerishiq" OJSC, starting from 2003, according to the indicators of 2020, the number of acts pointed in this field (52,202), lost energy recovery (166.9 million kWh) continues to increase.

Losses, including commercial losses, to the extent that they can be released is the method of carrying out and applying balance sheets. It is for this reason that it is very important to conduct research, to determine the methods of accurate measurement of received and consumed energy, to study the methods of carrying out balance reports for all stages, starting from 0.4 kV networks, and to give recommendations, in order to reduce non-technical losses.

Keywords: energy balance, commercial losses, illegal use of electricity, smart meter.

Non-technical (commercial) losses are defined as the difference between the consumed electricity and the measured electricity or billing amount. Analysis of these losses show that the ratio of non-technical losses to total distribution losses cannot be accurately estimated. Commercial losses depend on the technical condition of the networks, the social welfare of the

population of the region and the city, the organization of network management, the compliance of employees providing services to the population, etc. it varies depending on other factors.

Let's consider the structure of non-technical (commercial) losses in the table below:

Table 1

The structure of non-technical (commercial) losses

If we look at the table drawn up about the causes of non-technical losses, we will see that it mainly consists of unmetered electricity, payment errors and payment losses.

Table 2

Causes of non-technical losses

As can be seen, the commercial losses in the energy balance appear as part of the actual losses and are borne by the networks. [5]

In current literary source, commercial losses are determined by two main reasons: theft of electricity by

consumers; deficiencies in control of consumption and its payment. These losses are a complex component of total losses, mainly due to social and organizational factors. The fact that meter readings are not taken out

at the same time significantly distorts the monthly values of losses. [6]

It is appropriate to include the unpaid part of subscribers' receivables that are overdue for more than 3 years as commercial losses. Although the amount of these receivables changes every year, they are written off from the budget account after a certain time by the government's decision, but as a rule, they are not considered as commercial losses.

The level of commercial losses also depends on the organization of consumption control. Since this control is carried out by means of software in current time, the level of commercial losses of networks directly depends on the technical condition of the information base used, the service provided to it, and the perfection of the software. In the database, the following factors directly affect commercial losses:

- the absence of a specific transformer connection with the subscriber's identification code in the software;
- lack of connection of the transformer and substation with the supervising engineer;
- failure to install technical report counters at the head parts of the lines;
- failure to provide supervisory engineers with special devices;
- insufficient number of supervisory engineers and deficiencies in work organization.

The stolen electricity attributed to commercial losses, is formalized by the special enactment and additional payment accounts issued to subscribers, pursuant to the clause 8.17 of the "Rules for the Use of Electricity". [13]

In the last 5 years the status of the acts written on the restoration of commercial losses at "Azerishiq" OJSC (according to the EEIG) is as follows (picture 1).

Number of written acts and recovered consumption

■ number of acts written by years (number)
 ◆ consumption recovered over the years (mln.kWth)

Picture 1. In 5 years the status of the acts written on the restoration of commercial losses at "Azerishiq" OJSC.

Table 3

In 5 years number of written acts and report of recovered consumption at "Azerishiq" OJSC.

Years	Number of written acts			Report of recovered consumption	
	Population	N/population	Total	kWth	AZN
2016	31 132	7 065	38 197	128 707 287	9 099 267
2017	40 512	7 138	47 650	138 261 899	11 841 540
2018	42 162	7 219	49 381	170 846 497	15 770 031
2019	42 457	9 534	51 991	187 591 155	16 830 039
2020	43 982	8 220	52 202	166 975 391	15 212 485

As can be seen from the table and diagram, the number of written acts and the amount of renewable consumption provided by these acts has increased by approximately 40% in the last 5 years. Although the recovery of lost (stolen) electricity is a positive thing

for the networks, it is doubtful that these acts are written to the subscribers who are fed from the lost lines. Because reports and analyzes on the location of losses in 0.4 kV lines have not been carried out in the

networks for a long time, such a methodology has not been developed and approved.

In the two diagrams given below, the amount of total imbalance for the months of 2021 on the Khazar

district electricity network of Baku city and the Shirvan RETSI Saatli district electricity network and the consumption (kW /hour) comparison is shown.[15] (picture 2,3).

Picture 2. The amount of total imbalance for the months of 2021 on the Khazar district electricity network

Picture 3. The amount of total imbalance for the months of 2021 on the Saatli district electricity network and the consumption.

This comparison can also be made on individual transmission lines or TM (KTM). The result confirms that when experts draw up acts according to the rules of electricity use, it is not taken into account whether or not there is a loss (imbalance) in that part of the network. Another problem is that in the relevant clauses of the "Rules for the use of electricity" when the theft of electricity by the energy supply enterprise is enacted,

"within the claim period provided for in the Civil Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan for the working hours of the consumer from the date of the last replacement of the electricity meters or the check of the connection scheme" recalculation should be carried out"[13].

This allows networks to calculate additional consumption for up to 3 years per act. Therefore, network specialists should refer to the balance sheets to

detect electricity theft, and after inspecting the lost lines or TM (KTM), they should formalize the facts of theft. At the same time, we believe that it would be more appropriate to limit the total amount of acts (kWh) during settlement, the upper limit to the amount of imbalance in that part of the network, by making additions and changes to the relevant clauses of the "Rules of Electricity Use".

In general, the occurrence of electricity theft in electric networks can be conditioned by 3 factors:

- the motive of the theft;
- availability of technical conditions;
- imperfect legal framework.

If we consider these 3 factors separately, we will see that the existence of cases of electricity theft is not at all surprising. Thus, the increase in the prices of energy resources all over the world, the increase in inflation and losses make it inevitable to increase the tariffs of utility services, including electricity. This is one of the factors that provoke people to steal electricity in foreign countries, as well as in the former Soviet republics, where energy resources used to be extremely cheap.

The imperfection of electricity measurement systems in distribution networks, the fact that low-voltage networks mainly consist of overhead transmission lines consisting of open wires, create ample conditions for illegal interference (outside lines) and illegal network connections, resulting in theft of electricity. The current technical condition of networks is also one of the factors that create fertile conditions for theft incidents. This is more typical for internal power networks, ie 0.4 kV overhead transmission lines. As the cost of energy resources increases, the reconstruction and maintenance of the technical condition of distribution networks at a modern level is a strategic task. Solving this problem is very important mainly because:

1. Increasing the power of electric networks;
2. Reduction of electricity losses during distribution, including commercial losses;
3. Ensuring uninterrupted power supply in difficult natural conditions, as well as increasing the reliability and durability of power transmission lines.

Worldwide, this problem has been solved since the 1970s with the introduction of self-supporting insulated wires (ISVs) for 0.4 kV (up to 1000V) lines. This idea was first introduced in France and later developed further in Germany. Its design is very simple: all conductors have the same cross-section, are made of the same aluminum material and have the same insulation material. These wires, that is, phase and zero aluminum insulated wires, are wrapped in a package. This four-wire system is widely used in Austria, Germany, Great Britain, Ireland, Poland, Hungary and Scandinavian countries. The system consists of four aluminum insulated conductors that equally share the same mechanical pull load. The cross-section of the wires varies between 16-150 mm². Since the mechanical load is distributed among all four conductors, the breaking strength of the whole wire is quite high. Cross-linked XLPE polyethylene is used as insulation

material. This insulation is made of weatherproof, light-resistant, high-density thermoplastic polyethylene, making illegal intrusions impossible. At present, there are many standards of UIN cables in Europe and Russia, and they are even produced for high-voltage networks (10-35 kV) [10]. In our country, the application of UIN cables has been started since 2004 in "Bakielektrikshebeke" OJSC (at that time "Barmek Azerbaijan") as suggested by the author of this article. The proposal was supported by the Energy Institute of Scientific Research and Project Research of "Azerenergy" OJSC, and it was there that the first tests and familiarization with UIN cables were carried out. The application to the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan about the application of LV cables in the low-voltage (0.4 kV) electric grids of Baku and Sumgayit cities was considered and, despite the pessimistic opinions of many local and foreign experts (Barmek Holding), approval was given for its application as a pilot project. The fact that the issue was controversial was the fact that the introduction of UIP cables in Russia and Turkey was not started, and the financial capacity of the project was high. However, the local specialists of "Bakielektrikshebeke" OJSC were able to break the old stereotypes. In one quarter of Yasamal district of Baku city, the application of the UIN cable was started as an experiment. After the completion of the work, the 3-month measurements and the difference in the previous (before the application) indicators fulfilled all expectations. Commercial losses were at zero level, and technical losses (technical consumption) were below the norm. The results were presented to the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan, and it was decided to mass-introduce the cables in the entire country.

Currently, the implementation of 35 kV UIN cables in the Karabakh and East Zangezur economic regions, which have been liberated from the occupation of the Republic of Azerbaijan, is a matter of great pride.

One of the most common areas of commercial losses, or rather, theft of electricity, is multi-apartment buildings. Thus, the scheme of sequential distribution of electricity to apartments from the Soviet era and even in some newly built multi-apartment buildings is very primitive and creates ample conditions for theft (picture 4).

It was in 2004 with the scheme proposed by the local experts of "Bakuelektrikshebeke" OJSC (picture 5) that the internal electrical lines of more than 4,500 multi-storey (5-9) buildings of Baku were completely replaced and new copper cables were laid directly from the distribution box. Meter boards (panel) were installed on the II and VI floors. Balance sheets for multi-storey buildings were prepared, special software was developed for this purpose. It was the introduction of cables and the change of the electricity distribution scheme in multi-apartment buildings that changed the technical conditions for the occurrence of theft cases. Starting from 2005, theft cases and commercial losses in Baku began to decrease.

Picture 4.

In multi-storey buildings the previous energy supply scheme and settlement meter of household subscribers.

Picture 5.

Post-reconstruction energy supply scheme and billing meters for household subscribers in multi-storey buildings.

As for the legal issues, the situation is as follows:
Currently, the theft of natural gas, water and electricity in our Republic (by various means, it doesn't matter, outside line, tampering with the meter, etc.) is not considered theft according to the Criminal Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan and is not defined by its article 177. Legal violations in this area are regulated

by Article 189 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan and Articles 279, 281, 282 of the Code of Administrative Offenses.

In our country, the electricity purchase agreement between the state electric power enterprise and the energy supply enterprise, as well as the agreements concluded between the subjects of the retail market

(networks) and electricity consumers, only regulate the relations related to the supply and payment of electricity.

Currently, there is no special criminal-legal protection of the property of distribution networks related to electricity. The Criminal Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan does not define the signs and elements of the crime related to the theft of electricity as a specific type of product and property. This situation does not allow law-enforcement agencies to effectively prevent the theft of electricity, including proving the facts of theft in courts and compensating the thieves for damages. Also, this situation does not encourage the economic use of electricity, but also makes it difficult to carry out accurate accounting and evaluation of electricity.

Due to the lack of the right to independently apply sanctions against entities that steal electricity and the absence of an approved methodology for calculating damages, distribution networks cannot fully recover the damage caused.

Regarding the international experience, in 1985, an expert group was established in Belgium to study the issues related to theft and non-payment of electricity under the study committee on economics and tariffs of the international organization UNPEDE (International Union of Electricity Producers and Distributors) [16], which includes 11 countries. Experts from France, Italy, Great Britain, Norway, Spain, Denmark, Holland, Austria and Germany are included in this group. According to the report prepared by this group in 1998 [16], the term "electricity theft" is defined as the fact that, due to the consumer's fault, the electricity consumed by him is not fully accounted for (without a meter or when the meter is opened) or he violates the energy supply system in order to reduce his consumption measured by the meter. According to that report, only 4 countries - Italy, Great Britain, Spain, Ireland - believe that there is a problem of electricity theft. In Norway and France, electricity theft is prosecuted only under civil law, while in other countries criminal law or both apply. With the exception of the UK, Spain and Ireland, most countries have successful domestic legislation on electricity theft, which includes simplifying the punishment of those found guilty of off-meter electricity theft and non-payment of stolen electricity, including prosecution cherishes. In these countries, it is common practice in society to prosecute consumers found to have stolen electricity and to have the court order them to pay the full amount owed. Otherwise, honest consumers will have to overpay for the electricity they use to compensate for the electricity stolen by unscrupulous consumers [8].

One of the main measures implemented in order to reduce the commercial losses of electricity is the improvement of electricity metering systems. It also serves to increase the reliability of information about the structure of the electricity balance in electricity networks. A strategic way of electricity metering is the creation and implementation of a fully functional automated information and measurement system of commercial accounting of consumers in the wholesale

market and retail of electricity [10]. I should also mention that this automated software should also include accounting.

It is very important to take the following measures to get the best results from this software:

I. Technical measures:

- Providing normalized conditions for the use of smart meters;
- Replacement of useless and expired meters with new ones;
- Installation of additional measuring devices, including voltage and current transformers;
- Equipping consumers at all levels with smart meters;
- Placement (installation) of balance meters in terms of the implementation of tasks for the implementation of electricity distribution services;
- Protection of meters from external interference and unmeasured electricity consumption.

II. Organizational measures include the following:

- Evaluation of the current state of purchase accounting systems along the borders of networks;
- Creation of an automated database on electricity consumers;

With the exception of the UK, Spain and Ireland, most countries have successful domestic legislation on electricity theft, which includes simplifying the punishment of those found guilty of off-meter electricity theft and non-payment of stolen electricity, including prosecution cherishes. In these countries, it is common practice in society to prosecute consumers found to have stolen electricity and to have the court order them to pay the full amount owed. Otherwise, honest consumers will have to overpay for the electricity they use to compensate for the electricity stolen by unscrupulous consumers [8].

One of the main measures implemented in order to reduce the commercial losses of electricity is the improvement of electricity metering systems. It also serves to increase the reliability of information about the structure of the electricity balance in electricity networks. A strategic way of electricity metering is the creation and implementation of a fully functional automated information and measurement system of commercial accounting of consumers in the wholesale market and retail of electricity [10]. I should also mention that this automated software should also include accounting.

It is very important to take the following measures to get the best results from this software:

I. Technical measures:

- Providing normalized conditions for the use of smart meters;
- Replacement of useless and expired meters with new ones;
- Installation of additional measuring devices, including voltage and current transformers;
- Equipping consumers at all levels with smart meters;
- Placement (installation) of balance meters in terms of the implementation of tasks for the implementation of electricity distribution services;

- Protection of meters from external interference and unmeasured electricity consumption.
- II. Organizational measures include the following:
 - Evaluation of the current state of purchase accounting systems along the borders of networks;
 - Creation of an automated database on electricity consumers;
 - Organization of control over connection of new subscribers, legal and natural persons to the network;
 - Compliance with the dynamics of electricity consumption for months and years, calculation and analysis of electricity, actual, technical (technological) losses and imbalance in electricity networks;
 - Provision of remote automated simultaneous collection of data;
 - Providing the consumer with the opportunity to use a multi-tariff and differentiated menu when paying for electricity;
 - Maximizing the possibilities of using advance payment functions and payment control functions;
 - Provision of timely registration of events occurring in the electricity meter (light switching on, off, consumption modes, volumes, etc.);
 - Ensuring the ability to control the consumption mode of electricity (restriction from a distance, shutdown, etc.)
 - Organization of measurement of electricity used for production and economic needs of networks.

Thus, as can be seen from the preliminary results of research, the automation (programming) of electricity measurement systems has very important resources for reducing electricity losses.

Currently, the goal is to minimize commercial losses in front of distribution networks using modern methods, which can be achieved by taking the following measures:

- Automatically detect energy theft without involving any human power by developing an effective and efficient system;

- Develop a VEB-based mobile application to monitor all thefts, theft area and the direction of arrival to the theft area;
- To keep records of the total number and power of electric operators connected to the network by users in the server database and implement an online billing system;
- Develop a global WEBSITE that will facilitate analysis of thefts and provide analytics of theft incidents and probable theft area using various graphs and pictorial representations that can predict future thefts. [9]

Commercial losses are mainly caused by deliberate malfunction of meters or attempts to bypass meters by deliberate fraud, slowing down or stopping of meters, incorrect readings of meters or even illegal connection. The detection of these cases by means of modern digital information technologies and the formalization and payment of stolen consumption by means of relevant protocols (acts) is the biggest problem facing all the world's electricity networks. For this purpose, relevant studies are being conducted and software is being developed in all countries.

I consider it appropriate to apply the following method based on the law of current distribution in networks at the low voltage level after analyzing the processes related to commercial losses and theft of electricity in our country.

According to Kirchhoff's first law the algebraic sum of the currents at the nodal (branching) point of the electric circuit is equal to zero, in other words, the sum of the currents entering the branching point is equal to the sum of the currents leaving that point, and conventionally, the incoming currents are considered positive, and the outgoing currents are considered negative.

Picture 6. Branching of the current from the nodal point

If we take the current I_1 directed to the nodal point as positive, and the oppositely directed currents I_2 and I_3 as negative, then

$$I_1 + (-I_2) + (-I_3) = I_1 - I_2 - I_3 = 0$$

$$I_1 = I_2 + I_3.$$

Picture 7. Currents are measured by smart meters

$$I_{b/s} = I_1 + I_2 + I_3 + \dots + I_n$$

$$I_{b/m} = I * k_{ct}$$

In the picture: $I_{b/m}$ – the current of the balance meter;

$I_1, I_2 \dots I_n$ – current of subscriber meters;

k_{ct} – indicates the coefficient of the current transformer.

Considering the line loss,

$$I_{b/s} > I \sum_{1=N}$$

$$I_{\Delta} = I_{b/s} - I \sum_{1=N}$$

$$I_{\Delta} * U = P_{\Delta} (\text{kw})$$

Here: I_{Δ} – lost current;

P_{Δ} – power of electric energy; U – is voltage.

Thus, in order to detect the fact of theft, a system (measurement and comparison of current) is proposed, in which current distribution is carried out indirectly from the electric pole to the intermediate distribution box and then to individual houses, as well as to each apartment of multi-apartment buildings. The current is measured periodically in the distribution box and stored in the server database for each house using the GSM/GPRS module. At the same time, electric meters (smart) are installed for each house, which can measure the current value and send it periodically to the server database for each house or apartment using the GSM/GPRS module.

The installation (or unlocking) of the electricity meter, the user's information is entered and stored in the information database through the mobile application, including the address, geographic coordinates - latitude and longitude, as well as a photo of the user's house or area using mobile GPS. . If there is a difference between the amount of current from the distribution box and the electricity meter on the server, the fact of

theft is detected. This fact is shared with the address of the user and a photo of the house (territory) and geographic coordinates. The relevant structures of the networks register and send the fact of theft to the user by formalizing it online by means of appropriate protocols or acts. This system is similar to the way that the State Highway Patrol service, which has been successfully applied in our country, registers drivers who violate traffic rules on highways using RADAR and sends protocols online. I think that with the method I have shown above, appropriate software can be developed in our republic and successfully applied in electric networks, first as an experiment, and then on a mass scale.

This method can significantly reduce the commercial losses caused by the theft of electricity by users and, as a result, enable the profitable operation of distribution networks.

Conclusions

Nowdays, due to the market economics conditions, the formation of electricity balance in

distribution networks, the structure of losses, including commercial losses, analysis, study, their reduction or complete elimination has become the main factor of profitability of networks.

1. The improvement of the billing and technical accounting systems of electric energy is carried out in order to increase the reliability of information about the structure of electric energy balances in electric networks, and to reduce commercial losses of electric energy. The most productive way to do this is to make maximum use of the possibilities of digital information technologies.

2. The use of UIN cables has led to the reduction of losses, including commercial losses, in all high and low voltage networks of our country, and increased the reliability and stability of overhead transmission lines. During the design of networks of areas freed from occupation, in general, in urban planning, it is appropriate to make extensive use of UT cables and direct transmission of electricity to apartments from the distribution box, according to clause 8.17 of the "Rules for the use of electricity", the upper limit of the consumption lost (stolen) by electric networks is that TM- should be limited by the amount of loss.

3. Proposed method to prevent electricity theft by using modern information technologies Energy theft can be effectively prevented by providing online information to authorities or structures by finding out where electricity theft occurs. The proposed system will send an automatic message with its location and a description of the area to the corresponding structure as soon as the difference between the currents exceeds the limit of the current through the appropriate software.

4. The issue of accounting and settlement of unregistered electricity between subjects of the electricity industry (power plants) and consumers remains unresolved. Under these circumstances, it is necessary to develop normative-methodical documents, as well as to make changes with normative legal acts, in order to determine the amount of consumed (stolen) electricity that is not accounted for.

References

1. Steven Stoft. Energy system economy. Introduction to the design of electric power markets, 2006
2. Executive committee Electroenergetic CIS Council. Information bulletin no. 6. Electric power economy. Moscow. 2014
3. Vorotnitsky V.E. , Kalinkina M.A., Turkina O.V. Methodology for determining actual losses of electrical energy in electrical networks, 2006
4. Vorotnitsky V.E., Zhelezko Y.S., Kazantsev V.N. and others. Losses of electric power in electric power systems, 1983
5. Balametov A.B., Khalilov E.D. The results of energy saving measures in the power grids of the electric power system of Azerbaijan. Problems of energy #3, 2018
6. Balametov A.B., Khalilov E.D. Calculation, analysis and normalization of electricity losses in the power grids of the energy system. "ELM", Baku - 2015
7. Behcet Kocaman, The Importance of PLC Meters in Reducing Non-Technical Energy Losses, Bitlis Eren University, 2018
8. Nitin K., Mucheli U., Nanda S., Biswal. Smart Power Theft Detection System, Published -1 March 2019, Computer Science, 2019 Devices for Integrated Circuit (DevIC)
9. Bhavna Bhatia, Mohinder Gulati. Controlling electricity theft and improving revenue, Published - 2004, Reforming the Power Sector
10. www.enerdata.net- Enerdata (World Energy Statistics, Supply & Demand)
11. www.iea.org- The International Energy Agency
12. www.energsovet.ru
13. "Rules for using electricity", Baku - 2005
14. Energy of Azerbaijan. State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Baku - 2020
15. "Azerishiq" OJSC, annual reports of sales, control and balance departments, Baku - 2020.
16. www.uia.org/s/or/en/1100065583- UNIPEDA - International Union of Producers and Distributors of Electrical Energy